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ORCID 0000-0001-7890-485X

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF FORMATION OF INFORMATION COMPETENCY OF FUTURE MANAGERS OF SOCIO-CULTURAL ACTIVITY

**Lyubov Kravchenko,
Natalia Yaremaka**

У статті в руслі потреб сучасного суспільства в конкурентоспроможних фахівцях для сфери культури розкрито можливості компетентісного підходу щодо забезпечення якості підготовки таких фахівців. Під менеджментом соціокультурної діяльності розглянуто одну з порівняно нових спеціальностей, яка забезпечує поєднання соціального, культурологічного та педагогічного аспектів професії й відображує сферу відповідної професійної діяльності особистості, що реалізується у просторі свободи й невимушеного вибору кожною людиною шляхів забезпечення своїх потреб та інтересів. Запропоновано педагогічну модель, яка дозволяє цілісно уявити процес формування інформаційної компетентності майбутніх менеджерів соціокультурної діяльності, визначити його структуру, ієрархію компонентів, їхні взаємозв'язки і взаємодію всередині системи та із зовнішнім середовищем, урахувати необхідні освітні явища та процедури й спрогнозувати соціально та індивідуально значущі результати професійної підготовки фахівців цієї галузі.

Ключові слова: педагогічна модель, майбутні менеджери соціокультурної діяльності, інформаційна компетентність, інформаційно-комунікаційні технології.

Modern transformations in the system of higher education in Ukraine are connected with the spread of the ideas of European integration of educational systems of different countries, with changes in the strategies and structure of the educational sector, with the need for introduction of new social, scientific and pedagogical, telecommunication and information technologies of vocational training. The successful implementation of these socio-educational strategies requires the updating of traditional ways of mastering information, as well as the

development of software for teaching in higher education, the use of the latest information and communication technologies, adaptation of methodological developments for the effective formation of information competence of future specialists.

First of all, it concerns the professional training of future managers of socio-cultural activities, which should be prepared for the effective development of information flows and technologies at all administrative levels of the organization of culture and the leadership of groups of specialists in various spheres of socio-cultural activity. Their training needs to update the traditional content of cultural, socio-cultural, leisure and management disciplines, the introduction of new pedagogical models, the formation on this basis of the readiness of a specialist for effective self-realization in the field of socio-cultural and leisure activities.

The analysis of a complex of sources within the framework of the research problem has shown the urgency of the formation of information competence of future managers of socio-cultural activities. The simulation of the corresponding educational process is based on the theory of a systematic approach to the study of pedagogical phenomena (P. Anokhin, Y. Babanskyi, V. Slastonin, etc.), methods of constructing knowledge models in a subject professional area (I. Lerner, L. Friedman, etc.) Concepts of the technological process of the educational process in the conditions of continuous professional education (A. Nisimchuk, S. Sysoev, O. Pechot, etc.).

The purpose of the article is to describe the developed pedagogical model of training, which provides a component structure aimed at the formation of professional information competence of future managers of socio-cultural activities, their readiness for creative professional activity and effective provision of production functions, and the education of creativity of specialists in the measurement of common cultural values.

The analysis of the ideas and provisions of the methodological and theoretical approaches and the didactic foundations of the organization of the process of professional training allowed to fix the initial positions in the development of the model: in the paradigmatic aspect – the coexistence of different educational concepts; in content – systematic development of information competence in the context of higher professional education; in the structural – the project integration of cultural, pedagogical, leisure, administrative educational disciplines; in technological – application of information and communication technologies of training of a specialist; in organizational and management – the introduction of new achievements of socio-cultural management.

The development of a model for forming the informational competence of the future manager of socio-cultural activities envisaged the construction of a synergetic system characterized by: the possibility of self-organization and structural adjustment, active and continuous improvement of internal system connections; promising qualitative positive changes; dialectical interaction of components, subsystems, elements and parts. Thus, the proposed guidelines for designing the model led to the consideration of a complex of technological processes associated with its design, goal-setting, forecasting and practical implementation in the unity of the positions of personal, competence, integrative, cultural, marketing, system-synergistic approaches. The foundations for the goal setting of the training of future managers of socio-cultural activities made it possible to present the multifaceted goal of informational competence formation that would enhance the knowledge of future managers of socio-cultural activities (cultural, leisure, management), development of their abilities to apply information technologies in professional activity, crystallizing the clear personal needs of each specialist in self-development in the field of culture and leisure.

For the study it is important to note that the main tasks of informational competence formation are: enrichment of knowledge and skills in the field of informatics and information and communication technologies, development of intellectual and communicative abilities, implementation of an interactive dialogue in a single information space, and the tasks of

development of information competence are seen in a number of functions: cognitive, communicative, adaptive, normative, evaluative and informative [3; 5]. Considering the information competence of a specialist in the sociocultural aspect, we note that there is a mutually reciprocal link between each member of society and the information competence of society.

The theoretical analysis of scientific sources and normative documents on the problem of formation of information competence made it possible to realize its multifunctionality in socio-cultural, artistic-professional and creative-personal dimensions, which determined the integrity and indivisibility of the system of training, allowed to determine in the context of higher education the future manager of socio-cultural activity leading modern aspects of forming the information competence of a future specialist.

The humanistic aspect is aimed at forming an active position in the future manager of socio-cultural activity in understanding the world and national cultural experience, creating conditions for comprehensive self-development and self-realization in the socio-cultural sphere, developing the skills of using information technologies in the process of constructive cooperation for solving cultural and leisure issues, gaining dialogue skills communication in a team and with representatives of different ethnic groups, cultures, subcultures on the basis of equality, mutual respect and tolerance.

The cognitive aspect is oriented to acquaint students with the main provisions of the philosophy of culture, the dialectics of the historical development of domestic and world art, national traditions of regional cultures and socio-cultural activities, aimed at developing creative skills to use acquired knowledge, constantly enrich them, aware of the need for readiness for professional professional activities and inventions own creative style of work.

The value-orientation aspect provides assimilation of the students – future managers of socio-cultural activity – the value basis of a productive solution to various life and professional problems, the generation of criteria for evaluating leisure activities, phenomena and spiritual values of culture, which are aimed at the personal formation of a specialist in the field of culture and leisure, the upbringing of moral and ethical principles and norms of behavior, awareness of their own needs, interests and attitudes.

The integration aspect was realized the synthesis of certain elements of the professional consciousness of future managers of socio-cultural activity, to a certain extent, according to the criteria of the commonality of the general laws of information culture in the socio-cultural sphere, united the design and creative methods and forms of work that contributed to the improvement of orientation in the measurements of various artistic styles, periods, types of leisure and predetermined the unity of the goals of related disciplines in the general purpose of training a competitive manager of the leisure industry.

The main objective of the organizational aspect of training a specialist was constructive obtaining of cultural knowledge, the logic of selection and planning of the content of disciplines, the optimality of the ratio of classroom and independent work, co-creation of teachers and students, which formed the experience of self-control and self-discipline in the development of information competence.

Systemic and synergetic development of all components of information competence in the educational space predetermined their effective functioning in higher cultural education in accordance with the determined purpose aimed at the future manager of socio-cultural activity as a creative, independent personality in the socio-cultural environment, which is confirmed by the analysis and specification of the content parameters of cultural education.

Thus, the proposed model for forming the informational competence of the future manager of socio-cultural activity is in line with the scientific theories of pedagogical management of higher education, which serve as the basis for determining the following main tasks of the professional training of this specialist: the implementation of educational activities, which

implements the training of specialists of the socio-cultural sphere of certain educational and qualification levels for state standards; carrying out scientific and technical, artistic, cultural and educational activities and leisure activities; ensuring the implementation of a social order for the training of managers of socio-cultural activities; education of own scientific and pedagogical personnel. According to the positions of the selected methodological and theoretical approaches, the process of formation of informational competence of future managers within the limits of culturological vocational education is also conditioned by their active interaction with the external environment.

To identify the external context of the model, turn to the concept of «pedagogical management», which highlights the features of modern management of the pedagogical system, taking into account the interaction of external and internal factors, as well as the impact of the market of educational services and market economy [1]. The tasks of pedagogical management in the practical and technological aspect are the development of tools and methods that promote the search for effective ways of implementing educational goals, and the corresponding organizations of the activity of educational structures, where the result is a rise in the quality of professional training of specialists. The leading criterion for pedagogical management is the competitiveness of a higher education institution and its graduates in the modern labor market, reflecting the dynamics of the adaptation of the pedagogical process to rapidly changing external influences. Therefore, in the process of modeling, account was taken of the following types of factors: socio-demographic, natural, cultural; the amount of marketing information; labor market conditions; structure of the industry, availability and strategy of competitors; requirements of consumers of artistic, cultural or leisure products; political and legal foundations [1; 2]. The external parameters of the educational services market in education are defined: the nature of demand for specialists in the field of culture; legal conditions of university education; the level of integration of Ukrainian and world cultural education; the content and requirements of the educational standard, the structure of the specialty. The necessary factors that shape the internal management education system in the field of culture were also taken into account: the documented concept of goals and priority directions of educational activity; organizational structure and division of functions in subdivisions; scientific and pedagogical staff, information and material and technical resources.

Taking into account the above mentioned, the managerial context of the implementation of the model of information competence formation took into account all the considered relationships and outlined the management parameters of the educational process in relation to the organization and implementation of the mechanisms of interaction and performance of production responsibilities by the subjects of training, ensuring the operational control of the results in relation to the following main functions: *substantive content*, ensured the formation of information competence in the course of mastering the planned socio-cultural program D and related disciplines, whose content meet modern demands of social and cultural activities; *informational and technological*, which required the availability of educational information resources (educational and methodological complexes of cultural, pedagogical, leisure and administrative disciplines, library and methodological foundations, multimedia equipment, computer programs, electronic textbooks, etc.); *professionally-communicative*, which determined the requirements for the selection of competent teachers who are able to implement the stated goals of professional training of a future specialist in the organization of highly professional pedagogical communication; *administrative* method that enabled the effective implementation of modern information and communication technology teaching (method of mastermind (or mental maps), case method, project method, Delphi method, multimedia technology, Smart board technology, Internet technology, virtual technology, etc.).

In the process of implementation of the proposed model of information competence development of future managers of socio-cultural activities, theoretical conclusions of scientists

concerning the modular organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions were applied: the substantiation of the essence of modular studies (A. Aleksyuk, I. Bohdanova, A. Furman); the disclosure of the essence of the modular design of the content of training (N. Bordovskaya, G. Melnychenko, P. Podkassisty); as well as those in which the concept of modular learning based on the principles of dynamism, separate perspective, creative activity, parity, level methodological assistance in the allocation of modular elements of content is substantiated [5].

The urgency of structuring the process of formation of information competence on a modular basis is objectified by the dynamics of phased integration of socio-cultural project and educational activities in the gradual movement from reproductive to creative skills, a significant amount of professionally necessary cultural knowledge and practical skills in diverse academic disciplines, increasing social requirements for the professional training of managers of socio-cultural activities, possessing information competence, and the need for plan increase in the level of his continuous self-development and self-realization. The professional orientation of information competence of future managers of socio-cultural activities provided problems in designing the content of each module in the direction of motivating creative activities of students during the acquisition of socio-cultural learning material.

The modular construction of the content of information competence of managers of socio-cultural activity was based on universal pedagogical laws, expressed by a purposeful selection of educational material and its composition into target blocks, the completeness of educational material in each block, its comprehensiveness and integrity; ensuring the relative independence of the module and its logical completeness; methodological support to the process of mastering the material by students and feedback with the teacher.

In this context, the methodological goal of the modules of the formation of information competence was the acquisition of separate components of the content of each discipline that correspond to the professional and pedagogical tasks of learning, the selection of each module of the appropriate types, forms and methods of training, their coordination in time and the formation of an integrated methodological complex, which will lead to expected result. The main requirements formulated by G. Padalka became the condition for the conclusion of such a modular complex: adaptability of pedagogical methods to individual rates, needs and educational interests of each student, which became the driving force of activating learning and personal growth; mobility of the updating of educational material and methodological approaches that ensured timely overcoming of outdated forms of studying cultural, pedagogical, managerial disciplines and orientation on modern socio-cultural processes; the variability of the module construction, which revealed the specifics of cultural studies in the modifications of the «portions» of the material, the length of time to master the topic, an expedient way of sequential systematization of tasks; classification orientation in the choice of guidelines for structuring the content of the educational process (styles and genres of art, stages of artistic development of the individual); professional orientation, which ensured the integrity of the formation of information competence of future professionals [3].

The practical significance of the results of the study is contained in the development and implementation of the pedagogical process of higher educational institutions: organizational and methodological support for the formation of information competence of future managers of the leisure industry (curriculum of specialty 6.020101 «Manager of leisure industry, recreational resources and technologies», educational and work programs of disciplines «Technologies cultural and leisure activities», «Management and marketing in the field of culture», «Management of the leisure industry», «Management Information Technologies and a special course on the choice of students», «Information Technologies in the Leisure Industry». The materials can be used for the creation of textbooks, manuals, the development of training courses in the management of the leisure industry, cultural disciplines, cultural and leisure activities, in

the process of advanced training teachers of artistic culture in institutions of postgraduate pedagogical education.

The practical realization of the goals and tasks of the professional training of future managers of socio-cultural activities was ensured by the development of a block-modular educational system based on multi-level integration, which took place horizontally (combining the content of courses, interdisciplinary connections) and vertically (introduction of universal categories of complex metaproject integration).

At each stage of the formation of information competence provided by the pedagogical model, the leading forms of organization of work of students were used, which included: academic activity, academic activity with elements of professional tasks, educational and creative activity, educational and professional activities, research activities, socio-cultural and entertainment project activity. The gradual transformation of these forms of development from

reproductive to creative forms was the essence of the organizational and technological component of the model. The procedural component was reflected in a variety of control activities at each stage of its implementation: diagnosis of students' progress in academic disciplines; test of readiness for creative work; control test (current, semester, final, resultant).

Thus, the proposed pedagogical model of informational competence formation of future managers of socio-cultural activity has become the system-synergetic structure that provided favorable conditions for future specialists' development of components of informational competence (cultural-gnoseological, leisure-technological, axiological-motivational) subject-matter and practical-applied means implemented by a set of appropriate methods. Implementation of this model in the practice of preparing future managers of socio-cultural activities in the educational process of the Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University and a number of other universities of Ukraine allowed to investigate the state of formation of the investigated competence of future specialists, to measure it in a criterion and level, and to represent recommendations regarding the improvement of the specified segment of vocational training.

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КРАВЧЕНКО Л., ЯРЕМАКА Н.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

В статье в контексте потребностей современного общества в конкурентоспособных специалистах для сферы культуры раскрыты возможности компетентного подхода к обеспечению качества их подготовки. Под менеджментом социокультурной деятельности подразумевается одна из сравнительно новых специальностей, которая обеспечивает соединение социального, культурологического и педагогического аспектов профессии и отображает ту сферу профессиональной деятельности личности, которая реализуется в пространстве свободы и непринужденного выбора каждым человеком путей обеспечения своих потребностей и интересов. Предложенная педагогическая модель позволяет целостно представить процесс формирования информационной компетентности будущих менеджеров социокультурной деятельности, определить его структуру, иерархию компонентов, их взаимосвязь и взаимодействие внутри системы и с внешней средой, учесть необходимые образовательные явления и процедуры, спрогнозировать общественно и индивидуально значимые результаты профессиональной подготовки специалистов этой отрасли.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая модель, будущие менеджеры социокультурной деятельности, информационная компетентность, информационно-коммуникационные технологии.

KRAVCHENKO L., YAREMAKA N.

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF INFORMATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SOCIO-CULTURAL MANAGERS

In the article, the authors reveal the needs of modern society in the competitive specialists for the sphere of culture, the possibilities of the competent approach to ensuring the quality of training of such specialists. The managerial context of the implementation of the model of information competence formation took into account all the considered relationships and outlined the management parameters of the educational process in relation to the organization and implementation of the mechanisms of interaction and performance of production responsibilities by the subjects of training, ensuring the operational control of the results in relation to the following main functions: substantive content, ensured the formation of information competence in the course of mastering the planned socio-cultural program and related disciplines, whose content meet modern demands of social and cultural activities; informational and technological, which required the availability of educational information resources (educational and methodological complexes of cultural, pedagogical, leisure and administrative disciplines, library and methodological foundations, multimedia equipment, computer programs, electronic textbooks, etc.); professionally-communicative, which determined the requirements for the selection of competent teachers who are able to implement the stated goals of professional training of a future specialist in the organization of highly professional pedagogical communication; administrative method that enabled the effective implementation of modern information and communication technology teaching (method of mastermind (or mental maps), case method, project method, Delphi method, multimedia technology, Smart board technology, Internet technology, virtual technology, etc.)

Implementation of this model in the practice of preparing future managers of socio-cultural activities in the educational process of the Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University and

a number of other universities of Ukraine allowed to investigate the state of formation of the investigated competence of future specialists, to measure it in a criterion and level, and to represent recommendations regarding the improvement of the specified segment of vocational training.

The content and structure of the process of forming the informational competence of future managers of the leisure industry during the course of training was further developed. Interrelation between levels of general professional and informational competence of future managers of the leisure industry is revealed. The practical significance of the results of the study is contained in the development and implementation of the pedagogical process of higher educational institutions: organizational and methodological support for the formation of information competence of future managers of the leisure industry (curriculum of specialty 6.020101 «Manager of leisure industry, recreational resources and technologies», educational and work programs of disciplines «Technologies cultural and leisure activities», «Management and marketing in the field of culture», «Management of the leisure industry», «Management Information Technologies and a special course on the choice of students», «Information Technologies in the Leisure Industry»). The materials can be used for the creation of textbooks, manuals, the development of training courses in the management of the leisure industry, cultural disciplines, cultural and leisure activities, in the process of advanced training teachers of artistic culture in institutions of postgraduate pedagogical education.

The proposed pedagogical model allows integrating the process of formation of informational competence of future managers of socio-cultural activities, to determine its structure, hierarchy of components, their interconnection and interaction within the system and the environment, to take into account the necessary educational phenomena and procedures and to predict the results.

Key words: *pedagogical model, future managers of socio-cultural activity, information competence, information and communication technologies.*

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